

AI-Readiness Evaluation of RO-Crates by LLM Rubric Grading:

A FAIRSCAPE module for evidence-grounded scoring against the Bridge2AI AI-readiness criteria

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Abstract

We describe a FAIRSCAPE module that evaluates the AI-readiness of biomedical datasets packaged as Research Object Crates (RO-Crates). The module scores each crate against the twenty-eight Bridge2AI AI-readiness criteria, organized along seven dimensions, using structured rubrics applied by a large language model (LLM). The criteria are evidence-of-conformance specifications: conformance is determined by what the metadata says, not whether the relevant fields are populated. An earlier FAIRSCAPE evaluator performs fast deterministic presence/absence checks against predetermined fields but cannot judge whether field content substantively addresses each criterion. Each rubric in the new module specifies an intent statement, the evidence to consider, a three-level ordinal scoring rule, and a JSON output schema (score, rationale, evidence citations, improvement gaps). For each criterion, a compact evidence payload is assembled from the candidate crate and supplied to the grader with the rubric. Per-criterion outputs are aggregated into a release-level report across the seven dimensions. The module was applied to a Bridge2AI Functional Genomics (CM4AI) multi-modal pre-release dataset as an initial case study.

Keywords

AI-readiness; RO-Crate; FAIRSCAPE; metadata evaluation; large language models; biomedical data; pre-model explainability; provenance.

1. Introduction

The NIH Bridge2AI program defines twenty-eight practice-based AI-readiness criteria across seven dimensions (Clark et al., 2026). Each criterion specifies evidence of conformance rather than a particular implementation. Whether a dataset conforms to a criterion is a property of what its metadata says, not whether the relevant metadata fields

are populated. AI-readiness in Bridge2AI includes complete pre-model explainability, a necessary property for ethical and scientific deployment.

Our FAIRSCAPE framework (Al Manir et al., 2026) supplies an AI-readiness evaluator that inspects an RO-Crate (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022) against the twenty-eight criteria. It gathers predetermined fields, including DOI, license, Croissant RAI properties (Akhtar et al., 2024), and related entries, and reports each criterion as met when the targeted field is populated. The approach is fast, deterministic, free of external dependencies, and has been applied to the four Bridge2AI Grand Challenges.

The deterministic evaluator cannot read the content of each metadata property. It confirms that a property exists and is non-empty, but it does not validate whether the content fulfills the criterion. A bias statement of the form “The dataset has bias” is graded equivalently to a paragraph identifying specific bias sources and remedial actions.

Closing this gap requires a grader that reads what each property says. The AI-readiness criteria were written for qualitative judgment, which until recently only human curators could supply. Current LLMs can apply a structured rubric to prepared evidence and return a graded score with rationale and citations. The module described here implements that approach within FAIRSCAPE. It comprises two elements: rubrics that define what each criterion requires, and an evidence-assembly stage that pulls the relevant metadata from the RO-Crate for grading.

2. Implementation

2.1 Rubric specification

Each of the twenty-eight criteria is encoded as a self-contained rubric with four elements. (1) An intent statement, a concise paragraph articulating what conformance looks like in practice. (2) A “what to look for” section, a curated list of metadata properties, embedded references, and external URLs whose presence supports conformance. (3) A three-level ordinal scoring rule (0 = Absent, 1 = Partial, 2 = Substantive), each level paired with explicit decision criteria. (4) An output schema specifying a machine-readable JSON object containing the numeric score, a rationale, evidence citations drawn from the supplied payload, and gaps that would raise the score to the substantive level.

2.2 Evidence preparation

For each rubric, a compact evidence payload is assembled from the candidate RO-Crate. The payload contains: (i) all metadata properties enumerated in the rubric’s “what to look for” section, drawn from the release-level crate and its sub-crates; (ii) summary-level descriptors for each crate; and (iii) representative samples of relevant entities. Presenting

curated evidence rather than the full evidence graph keeps prompt length bounded, supports reproducibility across runs, and grounds each grading decision in explicitly identifiable fragments of the original metadata.

2.3 Grading

The grader is supplied with the rubric specification and the prepared evidence payload. It applies the scoring rule and returns output conforming to the rubric's JSON schema. Outputs are validated against the schema before aggregation.

2.4 Aggregation and reporting

Per-criterion outputs are aggregated to produce a release-level report across the seven AI-readiness dimensions. Each dimension report retains traceability to the underlying per-criterion scores, rationales, evidence citations, and improvement gaps.

3. Application

The module was applied to a CM4AI multi-modal pre-release dataset (Clark et al., 2024) as an initial case study. A pre-release version was used for this test because CM4AI metadata preparation has been upgraded significantly since the last official release in October 2025. We wished to both get results of the grader's effectiveness, and of our metadata completeness for the upcoming release. The grader's LLM version was Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4.6. Future runs are planned against Kimi 2.5 for comparison. The output included per-criterion scores, rationales, evidence citations, and improvement gaps that the deterministic evaluator had not surfaced. A systematic human-versus-grader comparison on the full set of Bridge2AI rubrics is the next planned validation step (see §4).

4. Discussion

The module rests on three established design choices.

First, the evidence-preparation stage extends the metadata extraction routine of the existing deterministic evaluator, which has been applied to the four Bridge2AI Grand Challenges. The new module preserves the deterministic baseline's coverage and adds semantic depth.

Second, the deliberate provision of selected evidence to the grader follows the same principle as retrieval-augmented generation (RAG; Lewis et al., 2020): enrich the model with the relevant material and require it to reason over that material. The implementation differs from classic RAG in that candidate evidence is enumerated by the rubric rather

than retrieved by embedding similarity. This choice reduces hallucination risk and keeps every decision traceable to specific metadata fragments.

Third, recent generations of LLMs have demonstrated the capacity to apply structured rubrics to free-text content. Reported agreement between LLM graders and human raters in benchmark studies approaches inter-human agreement levels for certain evaluation tasks (Zheng et al., 2023). Schema-constrained decoding further improves output consistency (Willard and Louf, 2023). Documented biases of LLM judges, including position bias and verbosity bias (Zheng et al., 2023), must be monitored.

The module does not yet have a direct human-versus-grader comparison on the Bridge2AI AI-readiness rubrics specifically. The CM4AI pre-release provided a single case study with a single model. The next planned step is to collect scores from domain scientists on the same evidence payloads and compare them against the grader's scores. Until that study completes, the framework's value rests on the three design choices above and on our own team's direct validation of its outputs.

5. Conclusions

Evaluating the AI-readiness of RO-Crates from presence/absence checks alone is inadequate, because such checks cannot determine whether the content of metadata fields substantially fulfills the criterion. The LLM rubric-based approach implemented here justifies each score with evidence from the metadata itself, and supplies curators and researchers with explicit per-criterion improvement steps. Applied to the CM4AI pre-release dataset, the module produced per-criterion scores and specific deficiency findings that the deterministic evaluator had not surfaced. We offer this approach as the next step in AI-readiness assessment for biomedical data. It closes the gap between structural compliance and semantic depth.

6. Availability

Source code and rubrics for this version, licensed under Apache 2.0, are available here:

https://github.com/fairscape/fairscape_grader

7. Funding

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8. References

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